

Studies on Imidazolinones : Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of 6-(4'-Substituted-benzylidene-2'-methyl/phenyl-5'-imidazolinon-1'-yl)-2-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone

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Manuscript received 4 January 1993, accepted 3 June 1993

Imidazolinones have been found to be associated with several pharmacological activities¹. 4(3H)-Quinazolinone and their derivatives are associated with diverse biological activities². This led us to prepare imidazolinone derivatives incorporating the quinazolinone moiety. Imidazolinones of the type **1** have been synthesised by the condensation of 6-amino-2-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinones with 5-oxazolone derivatives (azlactone) which was prepared by Erlenmeyer condensation of glycine with different aromatic aldehydes in presence of sodium acetate and acetic anhydride. 6-Amino-2-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone was prepared by the reported method³. The compounds have been characterised by elemental analyses, ir, pmr and mass spectral data. The products have been screened for their antimicrobial activity against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded

on a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer and ¹H pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₃) on a CFT-20 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

2-Methyl/phenyl-4-(substituted-benzylidene)-5-oxazolones were prepared by the reported method⁴.

6-[4'-(Substituted-benzylidene)-2'-methyl/phenyl-5-imidazolinon-1'-yl]-2-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinones (**1**). *General procedure* : To a mixture of 6-amino-2-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (1.75 g, 0.01 mol) and *p*-methoxybenzylidene-2-phenyl-5-oxazolone (2.79 g, 0.01 mol), dry pyridine (10 ml) was added and the contents were refluxed for 6 h at 140°.

The excess of solvent was then removed by distillation and the thick slurry was poured on crushed ice and HCl. The resulting solid was washed with cold water and crystallised from DMF, (65%), m.p. 300° (Found : C, 71.38; H, 4.43; N, 12.75. C₂₆H₂₀N₄O₃ requires : C, 71.55; H, 4.58; N, 12.84%); ν_{max} 3 350 (NH), 1 680, 1 580 (C=O and C=N str. of quinazolinone ring), 1 620, 1 650 (C=N and C=O str. of imidazolyl ring), 1 600 (C=C str.), 1 535 (NH def.), 2 950 (C-H str. of CH₃), 3 020 (C-H str. of ArH), 1 200 and 1 060 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C of ether linkage); δ 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.77 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.75 (1H, s =CHAR), 7.0-8.33 (12H, m, ArH), 8.49 (1H, s, NH) and 13.4 (1H, s, -N-CO- tautomeric); *m/z* 467 (*M*), 436, 376, 360, 345, 303 (base peak), 278, 256, 134, 122, 119, 91, 77 and 65.

Similarly, other imidazolinones were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF
6-(4'-SUBSTITUTED-BENZYLIDENE-2'-METHYLPHENYL-5'-IMIDAZOLINON-1'-YL)-2-METHYL-4(3H)QUINAZOLINONE (1)*

Sl no.	R	X	M.p. °C
1.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃	200
2.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃	240
3.	Cinnamyl	CH ₃	215
4.	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	CH ₃	205
5.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	CH ₃	>300
6.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	CH ₃	200
7.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	CH ₃	>300
8.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	CH ₃	250
9.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	CH ₃	210
10.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	CH ₃	>300
11.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	CH ₃	195
12.	Phenyl	CH ₃	>300
13.	2-Thienyl	CH ₃	230
14.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₆ H ₅	175
15.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₆ H ₅	>300
16.	Cinnamyl	C ₆ H ₅	240
17.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	C ₆ H ₅	>300
18.	4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl	C ₆ H ₅	>300
19.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₆ H ₅	160
20.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₆ H ₅	180
21.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	C ₆ H ₅	130
22.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	C ₆ H ₅	300
23.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₆ H ₅	185
24.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₆ H ₅	160
25.	Phenyl	C ₆ H ₅	295

*All the synthesised compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses; yields 60–70%.

Antimicrobial activity : The imidazolinones (1) were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup-plate method⁵ at a con-

centration of 50 µg using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. pyogenes* and gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella arogens*. The antifungal testing was carried out against *Aspergillus niger*. The compounds showed moderate activities (10–18 mm zone of inhibition) against all the bacteria and fungi. Under identical condition, the antibiotics ampicillin showed zone of inhibition 22–25 mm, chloramphenicol 21–25 mm, norfloxacin 21–27 mm, griseofulvin 20–25 mm against various strains of bacteria and fungi at a concentration of 50 µg. The compounds were found to be less active as compared to the standard drugs ampicillin, chloramphenicol, norfloxacin and griseofulvin.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Saurashtra University for facilities and to C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for spectral analysis.

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